

AN ACTION RESEARCH IN DOING SOLID WASTE SEGREGATION IN SITIO MALAKING PARANG, BARANGAY SAN JUAN, TAYTAY CITY, RIZAL

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ABSTRACT

Saving lives by preventing the severe impacts of floods through sustainable household solid waste segregation is of utmost importance. It is perceived as simple but not a habit of many Filipino residents. To understand the current level of knowledge and implementation of the effort, the researchers conducted action research among the selected collaborators in Sitio Malaking Parang, San Juan, Taytay City, Rizal. They tested the interventions through lectures and understandable and straightforward visual communication materials in Cycle 1 and the reinforcement through contests and prizes in Cycle 2. They observed that the interventions through lectures and understandable and simple visual communication materials about the nature, process, and benefits of household solid waste segregation in Cycle 1 improved the selected residents' understanding and knowledge. In contrast, the reinforcement through contests and prizes as simple incentives in Cycle 2 engaged the selected residents, considering the simple prizes and impact on their pro-environmental reputation to the habitual conduct of household solid waste segregation from December 2023 to the date of evaluation in June 2024. Continuous reminders and monitoring are expected to sustain the achieved level of discipline for said efforts.

Keywords: *household solid waste segregation, action research, education, reinforcement*

INTRODUCTION

Waste management is an environmental and pressing issue that demands immediate attention. To combat this, the Philippines has implemented RA 9003, or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act (Official Gazette, 2001). This act aims to provide systematic, thorough ecological waste management policies and programs to protect the environment and the public. However, despite these efforts, waste management remains a significant problem. Yulo-Loyzaga (2024) stated that the country generates at least 61,000 million metric tons of waste daily. The performance audit report by the Commission on Audit in 2023 reveals that the program's implementation of RA no. 9003 for two decades did not achieve its goal and objectives (Official Gazette, 2001). The failure was evident in the steadily increasing volume of generated solid waste and the many gaps noted in the program's implementation, such as the inconsistent execution of waste management nationwide.

Solid waste is the garbage or hard materials that are allotted for disposal, incineration, or recycling, like plastics, glass, food, appliances, biodegradable compounds, or non-biodegradable materials (Kaza et al., 2018, as cited in Merican et al., 2023). Solid waste management (SWM) is the collection, handling, and disposal of solid waste that is no longer useful or needed. Improper municipal solid waste management can lead to unhygienic conditions, causing environmental contamination and spreading diseases by rodents and insects. Managing solid waste is a complex task that involves technical challenges and administrative, economic, and social issues that require practical solutions (Nathanson, 2023).

As society continues to advance and expand, it is also confronted with several pressing environmental issues. The excessive production, over-consumption, and wastefulness of consumerism have led to overflowing landfills and polluted bodies of water, significantly impacting life and the environment. Merican et al. (2023) argued that PESI is one of the motivations and results of pro-environmental behaviors. Pro-environmental self-identity (PESI) is a self-concept about how individuals distinguish themselves or other people recognize the individuals who affect intention and several pro-environmental behaviors, like solid waste minimization based on past behavior (Ong et al., 2019, as cited in Merican et al., 2023). This study included the relevance of PESI in solid waste segregation.

To gain insights, the researchers coordinated with the San Beda University and the Social Action Program office to investigate the household solid waste segregation of the Sitio Malaking Parang, San Juan, Taytay, and Rizal communities. They asked the households about their main concerns regarding solid waste management. They also examined two major problem areas: the people's inability to follow the proper waste segregation system and the local government unit's limited access to waste collection.

In response, they thought of implementing an information campaign through education and reinforcement efforts to aid the residents' need for knowledge on proper waste management and more awareness of the alarming consequences of not making it a habit. Weiss and Tschirhart (1994) asserted that an information campaign is an effective

communication strategy for many citizens to achieve a policy result. It also attempts to deliberately shape public attitudes, values, and behavior to reach the desired outcome.

Lao et al. (2022) also confirmed that continuous training, reminders, and disaster and risk mitigation plans must be instituted in Taytay Rizal, considering its vulnerability to natural disasters, including devastating floods. This study is personal and dear to the researchers because it is one of the concerns that one of our partner communities in San Beda University Rizal, Sitio Malaking Parang in Taytay, Rizal, experiences a high risk to their lives and properties. They heard firsthand about the most significant issue our collaborators face as they commute to work or school daily. It is unfortunate, but every time there is heavy rain, the residents of the sitio, as well as those who pass by, are subjected to a muddy flood. This municipality is located northeast of Taytay, Rizal, bordered by Cainta City and Antipolo City. According to the collaborators, one of the reasons for the repeated floods is that most residents admit that solid waste segregation is not done consistently. Solid wastes, especially plastics, block the drainage and sewerage systems. It was also mentioned that the local government unit of Taytay, Rizal, handles solid waste or garbage collection once or twice a week. Aside from floods, the residents' surroundings are usually foul smelling, and flies infest the area, particularly the corner where irresponsible community members throw improperly segregated waste.

With collaborators' assistance, they used the realistic ORJI (Observe, Reaction, Judgment, Intervention) for deep reflection. The researchers faced a troubling situation requiring a more profound understanding, consideration, and thoughtful actions. This tool was also used to ensure that this paper is not biased and that no errors occur along the way.

They observed that the community of Sitio Malaking Parang, San Juan, Taytay, and Rizal had checked that two major problem areas in Solid Waste Management are people who do not follow the proper waste segregation system and the local government unit's limited access to waste collection. One of the collaborators mentioned that they try to categorize waste into two types: biodegradable and non-biodegradable. However, due to various factors, approximately 45% of the site's population must take the initiative in their respective households.

The researchers used both pure and diagnostic inquiry to comprehend these observations fully. Conversations with the collaborators led us to discuss the typical type of garbage they collect each week, their process of segregating their waste, the methods they use to dispose of garbage, and the collaborators' behavior concerning the concept of segregation and other associated motivations.

During the active discussion, one of the collaborators mentioned her difficulties as a member of their community's Task Force: Aksyon, Discipline at Lunas (ADL) and as a housewife, when it comes to solid waste management, is specific on reminding and ensuring that everyone in the vicinity follows the simple segregation scheme that they have. It was stated that only a few people are stubborn enough to refuse to segregate and dispose of garbage properly, even after several reminders. The researchers noticed that this problem

is leading us to a problem in maintaining the cleanliness and safety of the residents based on the various statements and stories from the selected residents.

Furthermore, they shared that as household heads, they must teach those who are young how to segregate waste from an early age rather than allowing them to throw small pieces of trash anywhere. The collaborators agreed with the researchers on the consequences of dismissing what they had observed of other residents not following proper waste segregation and disposal procedures; it is difficult for them to avoid flooding and the possibility of spreading disease due to wastes thrown anywhere collectively. The researchers also stated that they intend to teach them how to segregate their waste easily without confusing them, as well as how they can encourage others to do the same.

Research Questions

Most residents of Sitio Malaking Parang implement proper solid waste segregation poorly. Thus, the researchers aimed to address the following question: What functional interventions and their effects can improve solid waste segregation among the households of Sitio Malaking Parang, Barangay San Juan, Taytay, Rizal?

Specifically, they aimed to achieve the following objectives.

1. To determine the garbage source, type, and solid waste segregation practices.
2. To determine the reasons for the weak implementation of Solid Waste Segregation Management.
3. To introduce functional interventions on solid waste segregation that the Sitio can adopt;
4. To determine the effects of the functional interventions on solid waste segregation on the people and community.
5. To determine the behavioral changes among the researchers and the collaborators.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers utilized the action research design (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014). Action research has four steps: constructing, planning action, taking action, and evaluating action. Although these four steps are one cycle, they can be cyclical in numerous repetitions (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014). The researchers carried it out in two cycles to attempt to improve or solve the waste segregation of Sitio Malaking Parang.

They selected at least ten residents from Sitio Malaking Parang, Barangay San Juan, Taytay Rizal households as their participants and collaborators. The residents can either be barangay officials/volunteers or residents. The researchers used a non-probability purposive sampling design, considering the mother, father, or children of legal age as the inclusion criteria. The residents can describe the solid waste segregation practices routinely done in their residence and "sitio."

The researchers conducted pre- and post-surveys to know the crucial problem of the barangay residents regarding waste management in their community. A post-survey was also implemented after employing and carrying out the communication campaign to improve waste segregation, disposal, etc. Then, after identifying the residents' prime concern regarding waste segregation, the researchers conducted a semi-structured interview among the chosen ten households of Barangay Malaking Parang, Taytay Rizal.

They crafted the interview questions and assessed their content and the experts' validity before administering them to the study's target collaborators.

The Action Research Cycle

One of the best ways to cope with the continuously changing environment is to rely on action research while functioning by ourselves. In this study, the researchers utilized the action research design (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014) with two cycles of interventions to address the poor waste segregation of the residents of Sitio Malaking Parang in identifying the reasons for poor segregation, arriving at possible interventions, implementing them, and evaluating their effectiveness.

Action research has four steps: constructing, planning, taking, and evaluating action. Although these four steps are one cycle, they can be cyclical in numerous repetitions (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014). The researchers carried this out in Cycle One only to improve or solve the waste segregation of Sitio Malaking Parang. Action research brings together action and reflection, as well as theory and practice, in participation with others in pursuing practical solutions to pressing concerns" (Bradbury, 2015, p. 1).

To execute this Action research, they considered the spiral of action research cycle adapted from Coghlan and Brannick (2014).

Figure 1. *Spiral of Action Research Cycles*

The cycle comprises four primary steps, as seen in Figure 1. Constructing concerns teaming with collaborators to identify the problems. Planning action involves devising possible and concrete solutions. Explanations are considered, considering the significance

of the action plan's alignment with the context and purpose. Taking action paves the way for implementing the planned interventions and related activities. After executing the planned intervention, an evaluation was needed to assess the interventions' effectiveness for the residents of Sitio Malaking Parang.

Methods of Inquiry

The researchers conducted three methods of inquiry: first-person inquiry, second-person inquiry, and third-person inquiry.

The first-person inquiry will be commenced through participant observation gathering and documentation of reflections (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014). The reflections on the content, process, and premise focused on the engagement of our thinking and articulation of our thoughts as researchers and as parts of the community efforts (Dzage & Pierog, 2023).

Realistic ORJI. The researchers used a psychic process consultation using realistic ORJI (observe, reaction, judgment, intervention) to try to understand the situation, the needs of the selected residents regarding solid waste segregation, and possible interventions to enhance the implementation (Schein, 1999; as cited in Maw, 2021).

Second Person Inquiry

The researchers conducted pre-surveys to determine the crucial problem of the barangay residents regarding waste management in their community. A post-survey was also implemented after employing and carrying out the communication campaign to improve waste segregation, disposal, etc. Then, after knowing the prime concern of the residents on waste segregation, the researchers conducted a semi-structured interview among the chosen ten households of Barangay Malaking Parang, Taytay Rizal, through a focus group interview. A focus group interview is a form of qualitative research that takes non-numerical data and focuses on conceptual matters such as someone's attitude toward a challenge or the way they think to arrive at a solution (Podcastle Team, 2022).

This focus group interview allowed them to initiate an open and accessible conversation with ten residents from Sitio Malaking Parang, Barangay San Juan, and Taytay Rizal households as collaborators. They encouraged and listened to the collaborators share their insights regarding solid waste practices. The collaborators could either be volunteers (coordinators) or residents. They were chosen with the non-probability purposive sampling design, considering the mother, father, or children of legal age as the inclusion criteria. During the conversation, they described the solid waste segregation practices routinely done in their residence and "sitio."

Furthermore, the researchers adapted the question items utilized by Thyberg & Tonjes (2015) in the construction and planning phases and the question items of McAllister (2015) and Mericana et al. (2023) for the taking action and evaluation phases of the action research. The researchers took part in the different phases, especially in taking actions with

interventions (information campaign) and evaluating actions through interviews of residents, surveys, participant observation gathering, and documentation of self-reflection. Also, they adapted the transtheoretical model of (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983) to explain the involved change process observed in this action research.

To make it official, the interview questions secured the content and experts' validity before being administered to our study's target collaborators. Aside from collecting the collaborators' perspectives, the researchers recorded data during the focus group interview to document their sharing. Furthermore, interactive feedback was also carried out during the focus group interview and discussion of related issues concerning waste management.

Third Person Inquiry

Related to solid waste segregation management, the third-person inquiry is impersonal and actualized through analysis of accomplished details of inquiries as guided by models, reports, publications, and generalization (Coghlan & Brannick, 2014). The researchers used the following theories and tools: a third-person inquiry framework, an integrated trans-theoretical model, and a pro-environmental self-identity framework.

Lewin's force field analysis. Lewin's force field analysis is helpful in our problem-solving approach (Dzage & Pierog, 2023). In its implementation, force field analysis utilizes the driving forces or forces for a change and the restraining forces or forces against change (Rahmawati & Warmadewanthi, 2021).

System's model. The challenges, environment, structure, impacts, stakeholders, behavior, and modes will be documented and analyzed from the perspective of social thinking and the systems model (Conlon, 2021).

RESULTS

This action research took the researchers seven months to complete. The survey was completed despite the challenge of arranging time to meet their collaborators. Yes, common time and availability became the struggles in the conduct of this study. Despite these, ten (10) wives from Sitio Malaking Parang, San Juan, Taytay Rizal willingly collaborated with the proponents to provide the data needed for this study. The researchers needed to schedule a group and guided interview with the wives of Sitio Malaking Parang to carry out our planned interventions. They coordinated with Mr. Christian Caro, head of the Social Action Program Office of San Beda University Rizal Campus, to meet and interview the wives of Sitio Malaking Parang, Taytay Rizal.

The researchers agreed to address the set objectives in Cycle 1, and further reinforcement was provided in Cycle 2.

Research Questions 1, 2, and 3: Garbage Sources, Types, and Solid Waste Segregation Practices; Reasons for the Weak Implementation of Solid Waste Segregation Management

Table 1

Action Research Objectives

Objectives	
Cycle 1	<i>Identify the garbage source and type and solid waste segregation practices.</i>
	<i>Reasons for the Weak Implementation of Solid Waste Segregation Management</i>
	<i>Develop a systematic plan in order to adopt sustainable solid waste segregation.</i>

Most residents are not alarmed by the consequences of poor solid waste segregation management. Most residents have insufficient knowledge about the fundamentals of solid waste management segregation. Due to the demand for online shopping, 90% of the collaborators revealed that most of the garbage in their community is plastic and boxes from Lazada and Shopee, and they purchased biscuits and other kid snack products. One of the wives confirmed this: *“Pinaglagyan ng mga orders from Lazada and Shopee.”* (Placed orders from Lazada and Shopee.). Another wife shared about the source of their garbages: *“Ito po ay nagmumula sa mga pagkain na ating nabibili at niluluto kagaya po ng biscuit at sa pagkaing niluluto kagaya po ng Kangkong at pinagbalatan ng prutas at lagayan ng pinamili. Plastic na pinagballutan at papel na pinaglagyan.”* (This comes from the food we buy and cook, like biscuits, and food cooked like Kangkong, wrapped in fruit and packed with groceries. Plastic wrapped and paper wrapped.) Eighty percent of the wives supported the shared source of waste. Equally considered as sources and types of garbage are cans, fruits and vegetable peels, food wrappers, paper, and food debris and leftovers. Relative to this, one of the wives confessed: *“Sa mga taong walang hiya na nagkakalat imbis na tulad ng plastic bottles box ilagay sa tamang basurahan, tapon na lang kung saan.”* (For shameless people who litter, instead of plastic bottle boxes, put them in the right trash and throw them anywhere.) The collaborators agreed that they felt disappointed with this gesture and the practices of a few of their neighbors.

One of the wives of Malaking Parang had furthered expressed: *“Madalas po nagmumula ang basura sa mga pang araw-araw na ginagamit natin, katulad ng pagkain, plastic na ginamit na at iba pa.”* (Garbage often comes from the things we use every day, such as food, used plastic and so on.) Fifty percent of the collaborators have the same claim.

Environmentalists identified non-biodegradable solid waste, especially plastic garbage, as materials that could severely block and reduce the space of sewerages. This, in turn, could lead to severe floods. Said garbage was evident during Typhoon Ondoy in 2009 and even during Typhoon Carina in 2024.

When asked about this, the Malaking Parang wives said they segregate biodegradable and non-biodegradable garbage using a big plastic bag and a sack. Four of them claimed that they do it and even teach their children to do the same thing. They also sell the empty bottles and cans for extra money. One of these four expressed: *“Pinaghihiwalay naming yong nabubulok sa hindi nabubulok, bote, lata at plastic bottle ay sama sama sa isang lalagyan at binebenta.”* (We separate the perishable from the non-perishable bottles, cans, and plastic bottles in a container and sell them.) Aside from this, they also make fertilizers out of biodegradable wastes such as vegetables and the like. Aside from the individual household waste segregation, one of the wives said: *“May dumadating na truck para kunin ang basura.”* (A truck is coming to pick up the garbage.)

On the other hand, a few Malaking Parang residents still combined all types of garbage. One of the collaborators testified this when she answered, *“Katulad din sa iba, sama sama lahat ng klase ng basura.”* One of the wives also said they put their garbage in a sack and burned it: *“Nilalagay sa sako minsan at sinusunog.”* Like the expected proper waste management, 30% of the collaborators shared that they segregate their wastes properly to avoid scattered ones.

Regarding reasons for the weak implementation of Solid Waste Segregation Management, domestic duties restrict the collaborators' ability to segregate waste. Ten percent of the wives shared: *“Minsan hindi na po nasusunod dahil sa mga gawain sa bahay.”* (Sometimes, it is not followed due to household chores). The interview noted that they only segregate waste if they go to malls. One of the wives also shared that other people who scatter their garbage in their community hinder them from fully implementing and applying proper waste management: *“Palagi naman po pero sa ibang tao po kasi di maiwasan.”* (It is always but with other people because it cannot be avoided). In that case, the collaborators still advocate adequate waste management despite such circumstances that others are stubborn and reluctant to cooperate with the government. The collaborators still experience restrictions against solid waste segregation. The researchers believe that these concerns need to be addressed.

Solid waste segregation at the household level has already been initiated in Sitio Malaking Parang, San Juan, Taytay, and Rizal. However, the residents' knowledge of household solid waste segregation was not accurate and comprehensive, and they did not retain the importance of these actions. Thus, the researchers introduced them to the needed interventions to improve their practices of proper waste segregation.

Intervention. The researchers determined two essential interventions that they can contribute to improving the implementation of household solid waste management: to educate the selected residents with lectures and detailed photos of household solid waste segregation (Cycle 1), as well as to reinforce the correct solid waste segregation through contest and prizes to incentivize efforts of the collaborators (Cycle 2). More than simply giving them handouts and flyers on proper solid waste management is required to encourage everyone in the community to practice it habitually.

Figure 2. Force Field Analysis Before Intervention in Cycle 1

Restraining Forces and Driving Forces. The researchers decided to talk to selected collaborators through the help of San Beda University's Social Action Program. They actively discussed their reasons for and main concerns regarding solid waste management. At this time, they also conducted a lecture about the consequences and fundamental principles of an improved waste segregation scheme that is easier to practice and understand, even for children.

They applied Lewin's Force Field Analysis with the two specific objectives. As they tried to understand the reasons for a limited understanding of the segregation of household solid wastes among the collaborators, they found that the lack of clear instructions and education are the most determinant. A further interview with the collaborators found that their last lectures about the matter were long ago. They have no printed or guides in soft copy to confirm and perform the proper steps. Most collaborators wanted to be known in the neighborhood as "clean and responsible"; however, peer pressure was not regularly happening. The collaborators reported separating "too dirty" materials like diapers and spoiled feeds from other garbage. The garbage collectors with the LGU trucks segregate household solid waste.

Furthermore, the collaborators are not initiating activities to learn more about household solid waste segregation because of the lack of compelling reasons, like the outcomes of recent typhoons and floods, unlike the pressure shared by typhoon Ondoy in 2009.

Planning. Preparing for a target and desired change plays a vital role in the Unfreeze stage of Kurt Lewin's Change Management. For that reason, the researchers finalized the

objectives of this study and planned to conduct a survey on the issues of waste segregation among the residents of Sitio Malaking Parang. They held a Zoom meeting to discuss the agreed-upon objectives and proposed intervention. Then, they decided to have a plan of activities to carry out our research objectives and interventions.

Below are the planned activities they executed with the help of their collaborators, who were the ten wives of Sitio Malaking Parang. This plan tracked Lewin's Change Management framework.

Table 2
Cycle 1: Planned Activities

Change Management Framework	Activities	People Involved	Status
Unfreezing	Activity No.1 Finalized the objectives of this action research.	Proponents	Completed
	Activity No.2 Finalized the schedule for a Zoom meeting to discuss how the objectives and proposed intervention would be presented to the target collaborators.	Proponents	Completed
Changing	Activity No.3 Finalized a waste management seminar with the collaborators.	Proponents	Completed
	Activity No.4 Prepared a survey questionnaire to gather data from the collaborators after the proposed seminar.	Proponents	Completed
Refreezing	Activity No.5 Conducted the Waste Management awareness seminar.	Proponents, Collaborators	Completed
	Activity No. 6 Conducted a guided interview using a survey questionnaire.	Proponents, Collaborators	Completed

<p>Activity No.7 Implemented the agreed interventions of the information campaign (seminar) on waste management and segregation with the collaborators.</p>	<p>Proponents, Collaborators</p>	<p>Completed</p>
<p>Activity No. 8 Created a Messenger Group Chat with the collaborators to monitor the implementation of the discussed interventions.</p>	<p>Proponents, Collaborators</p>	<p>Completed</p>
<p>Activity No.9 Documented and evaluated the submitted pictures by the ten wives.</p>	<p>Proponents, Collaborators</p>	<p>Completed</p>
<p>Activity No.10 Reviewed and evaluated the results of implementing the interventions.</p>	<p>Proponents, Collaborators</p>	<p>Completed</p>

Table 2 presents the researchers' plans for this study based on Lewin's Change Management Principle.

Lewin's Change Management: *Unfreezing*

Activity No.1: Finalized the objectives of this action research

After a seminar on conducting action research, the researchers finalized the study's objectives. They drafted and revised them until they secured the San Beda University Research and Development Center Director's approval. Dr. Edralin instructed them to focus more on the manners or processes used to solve the issue.

After crafting the research objectives, they discussed the proposed interventions. The researchers came up with the idea of conducting a seminar to educate their collaborators about waste management and segregation. They also considered creating a messenger group chat to monitor the implementation of the waste segregation methods to be discussed in the seminar. They thought about having a contest for pictures of waste segregation to be submitted through the group chat. Winners were given prizes during the last meeting with their collaborators.

The planning stage allowed them to identify and decide on the study's necessities, value, collaborators' roles, needed theories, data-gathering tools, and other details. These decisions guided them in executing the study.

Activity No.2: Finalized the schedule for a Zoom meeting

They held four Zoom conferences to discuss executing this action research. The researchers discussed contacting our collaborators, holding their planned seminar, administering the data-gathering survey, and monitoring their waste segregation practices. Despite their time differences, they managed to put things in the right place and time, addressing our paper's concerns.

Activity No.3: Finalized a waste management seminar with the collaborators

They decided to hold a seminar about waste segregation and disposal to guarantee that their collaborators knew about it. They planned to coordinate the activity with Mr. Christian Caro, head of the Social Action Program Office of San Beda University Rizal Campus. With his help, they contacted ten wives of Sitio Malaking Parang and Taytay Rizal, who became their official collaborators for this study.

Activity No.4: Prepared a survey inquiry to gather data from the collaborators after the proposed seminar

To complete the needed tools for gathering data, they crafted their survey inquiry for their first and second cycles of interviews with their collaborators. These inquiries were floated and explained during the guided interviews with their collaborators.

They devised 13 questions (Table 3) with equivalent Filipino versions to better comprehend the first set of inquiries. The questions were the following:

Table 3

First Set of Guided Questions

English Versions	Filipino Versions
1. Where does your household garbage come from? What kinds of garbage do you usually have?	<i>1. Saan madalas nagmumula ang mga basura na nakokolekta ng iyong pamilya araw-araw? Anu-anong klaseng basura ito?</i>
2. How do you dispose of your garbage?	<i>2. Paano niyo itinatapon ang mga basurang nakokolekta o naipon?</i>
3. Are there bad incidents in your community caused by improper waste disposal? How did this affect you and your family?	<i>3. Mayroon na bang mga pangyayaring hindi masyadong kaaya-aya na dulot ng hindi maayos na pagtatapon ng basura? Paano naapektuhan ang inyong pamilya?</i>
4. Are you familiar with the proper waste segregation scheme? Where did you learn it? What is your understanding of waste segregation?	<i>4. Pamilyar ka ba sa proper waste segregation scheme? Saan mo ito natutunan at ano ang iyong pagkakaintindi dito?</i>
5. Is there a waste segregation policy in place in your barangay? What are the residents' reaction to this?	<i>5. Mayroon bang waste segregation policy na ipinapatupad sa inyong barangay/sitio? Ano ang mg naging reaction Ninyo bilang mga residente?</i>

6. When was the last time that you followed this strictly? What limits you to solid waste segregation?

6. Kailan ang huling beses na sumunod kayo sa waste segregation? May mga limitasyon bang pumipigil na gawin ito palagi?

7. Do you always observe the proper waste segregation scheme? (biodegradable and non-biodegradable) What are the most common reasons for not appropriately separating your waste and garbage?

7. Nasusunod ba palagi ng maayos nag waste segregation? Halimbawa, ang paghihiwalay ng nabubulok at hindi-nabubulok na basura? Sa inyong palagay, ano ang madalas na dahilan kung bakit hindi ito nasusunod ng maayos?

8. Do you see your neighbors following proper waste segregation in your neighborhood? What do you do if you see them putting all types of waste together in one container?

8. Nakikita mo bang sumusunod ang iyong mga kapitbahay sa proper waste segregation? Kung sakali ay nakita mo silang pinagsasama lamang ang lahat ng basura sa isang lagayan, ano ang iyong naging reaksyon o aksyon dito?

9. Why do you believe many communities members do not adhere to the proper segregation scheme?

9. Sa inyong palagay bakit marami sa inyong komunidad ang hindi sumusunod o gumagawa ng maayos na paghihiwalay ng basura?

10. Have you considered the idea and possibilities of what would happen if you strictly followed the proper segregation scheme from the start? What possibilities could you imagine?

10. Bilang miyembro ng isang komunidad, sumagi n ba sa iyong isipan kung ano ang mangyayari kung ikaw at ang lahat ng iyong kapitbahay ay sumusuno sa tamang paraan ng pagtatapon ng basura mula umpisa? Anu-anong mga bagay ang iyong naiisip patungkol dito?

11. Could you have done something to remind Your family and neighbors, what about proper waste segregation?

11. Mayroon ka na bang ginawa upang ipaalaala sa iyong pamilya at kapitbahay ang tungkol sa tamang paghihiwalay ng mga basura?

12. What will encourage you to segregate waste in your residence?

12. Sa iyong tingin, ano ang mga bagay na maghihikayat sa iyo at sa iba na maghiwalay at magtapon ng basura sa maayos at tamang pamamaraan?

13. Is there a change in your image or reputation if you do solid waste segregation? What is that change?

13. Mayroon bang magiging pagbabago sa iyong imahe or reputasyon kung ikaw ay sususod sa mga panukala sa tamang pagtatapon ng basura? Ano sa tingin mo, ang mga pagbabagong ito?

Furthermore, they also crafted the second set of inquiries, which they administered after implementing the interventions. The inquiry was composed of two major questions with seven sub-sets each. The questions focused on the benefits and incentives of sustainable waste management and their practices on managing the benefits of proper

waste management and disposal. The same goes for the second set of guided questions; they also provided the Filipino translation.

As regards the sub-sets of the significant questions, the contexts include:

1. Cost Savings (*Pagtitipid sa Gastos*);
2. Economic Advantage (*Kalamangan sa Ekonomiya*);
3. Improved Health and Safety (*Pinabuting kalusugan at kaligtasan*);
4. Improved Community Engagement (*pinahusay na pakikipag-ugnayan sa komonidad*);
5. Enhanced and Improved Resources (*Pinahusay na mga mapagkukunan*);
6. Positive Social Effects (*Positibong epekto sa Lipunan*);
7. Financial Benefits (*Mga benepisyo sa Pinansyal*).

Lewin's Change Management: *Changing*

Activity No. 5: Conducted the Waste Management awareness seminar

On December 2, 2023, the researchers finally held the seminar on Proper Waste Segregation at San Beda University, Rizal campus. The activity was made possible through Mr. Christian Caro, head of the Social Action Program Office of San Beda University Rizal Campus.

During the seminar, ten wives from Sitio Malaking Parang, Taytay Rizal, attended and shared their observations about waste segregation practices in their community. They also participated in the question-and-answer portion of the seminar, which helped the researchers gather data in addition to the information generated by the survey inquiry.

Activity No.6: Conducted a guided interview using a survey inquiry

Stemming from the seminar, the researchers conducted a guided interview with their collaborators. The interview took over an hour because they needed to explain each question in Filipino. The wives of Sitio Malaking Parang clarified the questions' details and confirmed whether they answered them correctly. On the brighter side, the researchers gathered all the data needed to answer the objectives and analyze the problem they chose to investigate.

Activity No.7: Implemented the agreed interventions

As explained during the seminar the researchers conducted with the wives of Sitio Malaking Parang; they started implementing the segregation of biodegradable and non-biodegradable garbage in their community. They instructed them to provide a sack or any available stuff to segregate their garbage accordingly. The researchers also explained the value of scrap, as they can generate additional income from it. Thus, they also provided a space aside from the biodegradable and non-biodegradable wastes.

The implementation of the waste segregation they learned from the researchers' seminar was monitored through the group chat they created with the ten wives. They took pictures of their practices and sent them to their GC. As a matter of getting connected with

them, the researchers sent them messages and regards about their way of segregating their garbage.

Consequently, they sustained their practices within seven months of conducting this study. During the last meeting, the researchers encouraged them to continue practicing proper waste segregation with or without the presence of research.

Activity No.8: Created a Messenger Group Chat

As a matter of reiteration, the researchers created a group chat to monitor the implementation of the interventions they provided to their collaborators. The GC served as an open line of communication between them and the wives of Sitio Malaking Parang. It helped them to guarantee that their collaborators worked with them to achieve the goals of this study. True enough, they practiced and implemented what they learned in the seminar.

Lewin's Change Management: *Refreezing*

Activity No.9: Documented and evaluated the submitted pictures by the ten wives

During this stage of Refreezing, the researchers consolidated the submitted pictures of waste segregation as evidence. They picked the best three and prized them with grocery items during their last meeting with them.

The researchers concluded that their waste management interventions were implemented for a few months. The collaborators saw the sustainable impact of their effort on their community since they continue to practice waste segregation. During the researchers' last meeting, they testified that they continued doing it to their advantage and even taught their family members to follow the process. This testimony of their collaborators affirmed the fulfillment of the research goals and objectives.

Activity No.10: Reviewed and evaluated the results of implementing the interventions

The researchers conducted a qualitative assessment through a focused group interview to validate their waste segregation practices. They prepared questions for them to answer, and they needed to explain every question to facilitate comprehension. Finally, after the last guided interview and meeting with their collaborators, they tabulated the gathered data and began analyzing them.

Research Question 4. Effects of the Functional Interventions on Solid Waste Segregation on the People and Community

Through a survey conducted over the past seven months, the researchers' collaborators have reported significant benefits from implementing proper waste segregation. More than half of the ten wives from Sitio Malaking Parang indicated that they have realized considerable financial savings and benefits from their waste management efforts. One participant noted, "*Kahit papano nagkakaroon kami ng pera dahil sa mga lata, plastic, at iba pang bagay galing sa basura,*" (*Somehow, we make money because of cans, plastic, and other things from the garbage*) which was echoed by others. Another shared,

“Dahil sa pagrerecycle, hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa mga gagamiting paso at lagayan ng halaman. Sa recycled material, maaaring mong ibenta ang ilan at may extra pang merienda for kids. At maaari mong magamit yung recycled materials bilang paso, pencil organizer, at marami pang iba. Hindi mo kailangang gumastos dahil may pera sa basura.” (Because of recycling, there is no need to spend for used pots and plant pots. With recycled material, you can sell some and have extra snacks for kids. And you can use recycled materials as pots, pencil organizers, and many others. You don't have to spend because there's money in the trash). These statements underscore how sustainable waste segregation has positively impacted their household budgets and expenses.

Additionally, the wives reported improvements in health and safety within their community. One notable comment was, *“Napansin ko po na these past few months, yung mother ko na may hika, hindi na gaano nagreklamo tungkol sa amoy ng basura dahil hindi na sama-sama yung maaaring dahilan ng hindi magandang amoy.”* (I noticed that these past few months, my mother who has asthma, doesn't complain as much about the smell of the garbage because the things that could be the cause of the bad smell are no longer together.) Other collaborators confirmed this, noting reduced flies and insects around their area since they began proper waste management practices.

The community contest also fostered increased engagement and positive social effects. Collaborators have actively encouraged their neighbors and friends to adopt proper waste segregation, sharing insights from our initial lecture. One participant mentioned, *“Naenganyo ko po ang aking mga anak na itapon ang mga basura sa tamang lagayan, tulad ng papel, plastic, at mga dahoon,”* (.” (I have encouraged my children to throw the garbage in the right place, such as paper, plastic, and leaves,) while another added, *“Sa pamamagitan po ng programang ito, kahit araw-araw ako nagpaalala sa mga bata, natututo sila kahit papaano. Nagkaroon ng pagkakasundo sa amin”* Through this program, I reminded the children every day, learning they somehow there was a reconciliation between us.)

Furthermore, the research collaborators have become more resourceful and creative with their recycled materials. One wife reported, *“Yung mga malilinis na balat ng biscuit, tsitsirya, at pancit canton ay nagagawa naming palaman para maayos ang mga unan at sirang stuffed toys ng mga bata.”* (The clean wrapper of biscuits, chips, and pancit canton we can stuff to fix the children's pillows and broken stuffed toys) Another added, *“Ang asawa ko po ay traysikel driver, kaya po yung mga charger na sira itinatabi ko sapagkat magagamit niya ang mga wires. At dahil sa recycled materials, may mga projects ang mga anak ko na makukuha doon at hindi na kailangan bumili ng bagong kagamitan.”* (My husband is a tricycle driver, so I keep the broken chargers because he can use the wires. Furthermore, because of the recycled materials, my children have projects that can be done there, and there is no need to buy new equipment.) These examples highlight how the waste management program has inspired innovative uses for recycled materials, demonstrating increased resourcefulness and creativity among participants.

The benefits of the waste segregation program, including significant financial savings and improved health, are clear. The collaborators' feedback on the second intervention, the

picture contest, revealed a consensus that such initiatives are highly effective in fostering long-term commitment to proper waste management practices.

They shared their experiences and highlighted the motivating impact of the contest. One collaborator noted, *“Yes, dahil sa programang ito ako po ay namotivate gawin ang isang bagay na to. Dahil sa isang paliksahang ilagay sa tamang lagayan ang basura. Sobrang laki ng naitulong sa akin at sa aking mga kapitbahay ang programang naituro sa amin.”* (Yes, because of this program I was motivated to do something. Because of a contest to put the trash in the right container. The program taught to us has helped me and my neighbors a lot.) Another emphasized the dual benefits of the contest: *“Yes po, dahil mas pinagbuti po ang aking pag-aayos ng mga basura dahil hindi lang po sa makukuhang prizes kung hindi dahil na rin po sa kaligtasan at magandang kalusugan ng aking pamilya. At kung mapapanatiling maayos ang pag-aayos ng basura, magiging maganda ang kapaligiran.”* (Yes, because I improved my garbage disposal not only because of the prizes but also because of the safety and good health of my family. And if waste management is maintained properly, the environment will be good.) Lastly, one of the wives appreciated the recognition received, stating, *“Yes, dahil alam mo na maappreciate ka ng mga tao sa ginawa mo. Nakatulong para gawin mo yung best mo pero hindi dapat laging may hinihintay na kapalit. Always do your best with a wide smile.”* (Yes, because you know that people will appreciate what you did. It helped you do your best, but you shouldn't always expect something in return. Always do your best with a wide smile.)

These echo the contest's positive impact on improving waste management practices. The program increased motivation, consistency, and community participation and engagement by incorporating competitive elements and acknowledging participants' efforts and hard work. It resulted in tangible benefits such as financial savings and improved health, promoting a culture of proactive involvement and mutual support.

Research Question 5. Behavioral Changes that Occurred among the Researchers and the Collaborators

What changed for the Researchers?

This action research has fostered collaboration and enabled team members to exchange ideas. It provided them a valuable platform to discuss and address the significant challenge of waste segregation. Previously, their approach was essentially individualistic; however, this research facilitated a collective effort, allowing the researchers to share their insights and educate others effectively. This collaborative environment diminished any initial discomfort associated with promoting new practices and empowered them to advocate for cleaner and safer environmental practices within our community.

The research process enriched their understanding by introducing new concepts, strategies, and skills to benefit future research endeavors. Most critically, they learned that the success of such initiatives hinges on collective effort rather than isolated endeavor. The synergy of support and camaraderie among team members made the research more enjoyable and significantly enhanced its impact. This experience underscored the

importance of collaboration in achieving meaningful outcomes and reinforced the notion that effective and sustainable solutions emerge from a unified, engaged approach.

What changed in others/collaborators?

This action research has profoundly illuminated the diversity inherent in our world, revealing how individuals differ in their reactions and approaches to shared goals. The researchers initially harbored concerns that their selected collaborators might be hesitant or unwilling to engage. However, their apprehensions were unfounded. The collaborators demonstrated unwavering support and enthusiasm throughout the research journey for the various interventions the researchers implemented.

Their commitment was evident as they fully embraced and participated in the initiatives. Many expressed their initial doubts about the feasibility of consistently and effectively managing their waste, yet they were pleasantly surprised by their ability to do so. Moreover, they were very satisfied with sharing their newfound knowledge with other community members. While a novel experience for them, this action research has served as a powerful motivator, reinforcing their belief that collective effort can overcome challenges and pave the way for a more sustainable future.

This journey has underscored the significance of collaboration and mutual support. It has shown that when people work together with a shared vision, they can achieve remarkable outcomes, demonstrating that seemingly insurmountable goals can become attainable with concerted effort. This experience has fostered a stronger sense of community and reinforced the importance of perseverance and cooperation in striving for sustainable development.

What changed in the organization?

Initially, the researchers' ambition was modest: to assist the members of their chosen community in their waste management practices. However, through their collaboration with the Office of the Social Action Program, this endeavor has evolved into a robust and ongoing partnership. This initiative has deepened their connection with the community and significantly altered their understanding of sustainability. The support from the institution has broadened their perspective, enabling them to effectively promote the principles articulated in Pope Francis' "Laudato Si". As a Catholic institution committed to fostering a holistic community and nurturing its members through inculcating Benedictine values, San Beda University has played a pivotal role in advancing these ideals. The researchers take great pride in their institution's contribution to effecting positive change, aligning with their mission to advocate for sustainable development and environmental stewardship.

This experience has reinforced the institution's dedication to social responsibility and community engagement. By extending its outreach and applying its values to real-world challenges, it has supported the community and exemplified the transformative impact of collaborative efforts in achieving sustainability goals. San Beda's involvement has thus been

instrumental in bridging its educational objectives with tangible benefits for the community, furthering its collective mission for a more sustainable and ethically informed future.

DISCUSSION

Notably, during the first cycle of data gathering, the researchers conducted a lecture about proper waste segregation that proposed a more specific and easy-to-understand way of segregating waste. At the same time, they held a group interview with their collaborators. During the group and guide interview, they simplified and explained the questions and translated them into the collaborator's dialect for better comprehension. At first, a few of them appeared hesitant to work with the researchers but ended up supportive until the last data-gathering stage. The researchers even created a group chat exclusively for collaborators to monitor the progress of the proposed scheme and solutions for improper waste management in their community.

Content Reflection. Coghlan (2019) pointed out that content reflection is where you think about the issues and what is happening. Household solid waste segregation efforts were underrated until severe floods happened again, as in the case of the flood caused by Carina on July 22, 2024. Along the fences were hanging plastic and non-biodegradable garbage. The researchers realized that the accumulation of impediments to sewerages increased with time. When the collaborators were asked what garbage to contain together, the answers needed to be more consistent, although they appeared simple. Unless the understanding of household solid waste segregation and its benefits is enhanced, they realize there is a weak implementation of said efforts.

Process Reflection. Coghlan (2019) clarified that process reflection involves thinking about strategies and procedures and how things are done. As the researchers interacted with the collaborators, they realized that clarity, simplicity, and visual communication are keys to educating the residents about household solid waste segregation.

Premise Reflection. Coghlan (2019) also described premise reflection as where you critique the underlying assumptions and perspectives. The researchers realized that highlighting the importance of household solid waste segregation was the most influential driver for the residents to engage in the orientation about the efforts. By checking their current understanding of it, they assessed the level of interventions that they could do. The researchers considered that they could not trust a person's memory about household solid waste segregation details. They recognized that the ready availability of visual guides about the garbage to be contained together, color-coded containers, and the understanding of the concepts regarding recyclable, non-recyclable, biodegradable, and non-biodegradable solid waste are the essential concepts to ground the knowledge of the residents.

Evaluation. Figure 3 below summarizes the root causes, factors, bases for interventions, and benefits.

Figure 3. External, Internal, and System Model (Adopted from Bertalanffy 1940, 1968)

On the other hand, the evaluation and intervention conducted during the cycle yielded several positive results, which strongly supported the achievement of the paper's objectives.

The researchers first and initial intervention gave them the idea that the collaborators have a solid foundation for segregating waste properly. However, since they only had a few participants, they decided to proceed to Cycle 2, where they conducted a contest in which the collaborators had to include all the people in their household and their neighbors in segregating waste properly and sending an image of their waste management area.

The objectives concern the residents' positive motivation to perform correct and consistent efforts, considering the inappropriateness of imposing penalties or fines for not doing so. The positive motivation through photo contests was also determined using the Realistic ORJI. The primary issue is the lack of motivation to segregate household solid wastes consistently.

Conclusions

In the final analysis, the success of this waste management initiative underscores the pivotal role of motivation and community engagement in maintaining effective environmental practices. The positive results observed among the researchers and collaborators demonstrate the significant impact of integrating educational strategies with incentive-based activities. This approach presents a valuable model for other communities aiming to achieve comparable benefits and emphasizes the importance of ongoing commitment to environmental stewardship.

Recommendations

With clarity, success stories, and testimonials from collaborators, other LGUs, NGOs, universities, and barangays can adopt programs and campaigns in other communities. These stakeholders are encouraged to include them in their priorities, budgets, and investments. More prominent communities, societies, and organizations need role models and systematic processes to effect a change in sustainable household solid waste segregation. This action research raised the importance of dilemmas, difficulties, losses, and problems, which drives stakeholders to embrace such efforts. The researchers encourage IBED San Beda University to replicate this action research in additional Sitio, barangay, and cities. Considering the feasibility of the action research, the replication and cascading of the interventions and program are very doable. The researchers expect that volunteerism and LGU support are beneficial for institutionalizing the action research and studied interventions.

The presentation and publication of this action research to wider groups of stakeholders expand the reach of its valuable message and purpose. Future researchers can also perform and compare their programs and interventions and share their critical insights and reflections to improve the implementation of sustainable household solid waste segregation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the research, ethical approval was obtained from the university's Research Ethics Board. Written consent forms were provided to all collaborators. After receiving their consent and assuring them of anonymity and confidentiality, they were invited for a Focused group interview. The researchers then assured the confidentiality of their personal information by not mentioning their names.

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